

MOLECULAR DOCKING STUDIES ON SECONDARY METABOLITES OF INDONESIA HERBAL MEDICINE TO REDUCED PPAR α / γ ON TYPE II DIABETES MELLITUS

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Abstract

The prevalence of Diabetes Mellitus increases every year. From 2010 to 2030 the loss of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) due to Diabetes Mellitus is estimated to be around 1.7 trillion dollars and this condition will affect the government's efforts in attaining Indonesia's Golden Generation in 2045. Type II Diabetes Mellitus is occurs when beta pancreatic cells produce insulin but the cells can't use it as well as they should. It call Insulin resistance. Aleglitazar is Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptor α/γ (PPAR α/γ) agonist has potential treatment of hyperglycaemia in patients with Type II Diabetes Mellitus. However, aleglitazar has a severe side effect of peripheral edema, weight gain, and congestive heart failure. Therefore we need new substances to change the Aleglitazar made from Indonesian herbal medicine with the study of molecular docking. Some natural compounds from plants inhibit glucose absorption by inhibiting intestinal α -amylase and α -glucosidase. Molecular docking studies have been carried out against the target, PPAR α/γ receptor. The results of molecular docking showed that the natural compounds that have the lowest Free Energy Binding value and best hydrogen bond is Andrographolide ($\Delta G = -8.46$ kcal/mol). We can concluded that *Tinospora crispera* (Brotowali) is an Indonesia Herbal Medicine that has the best antidiabetic activity.

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1. Introduction

Diabetes Mellitus is a complex, chronic illness requiring continuous medical care with multifactorial risk-reduction strategies beyond glycemic control. Diabetes Mellitus can be classified into the following general categories: Type II Diabetes Mellitus; Type II Diabetes Mellitus; Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM); specific types of diabetes due to other causes, e.g., monogenic diabetes syndromes; diseases of the exocrine pancreas; and drug or chemical-induced diabetes. Type II Diabetes Mellitus occurs because the progressive loss of β -cell insulin secretion frequently on the background of insulin resistance [1]. It is the 5th fastest growing disorder. The prevalence of Diabetes Mellitus in 2015 reached 415 million people, and estimated in 2040 the number will increase 4-fold to 642 million people [2]. From 2010 to 2030 the loss of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) due to Diabetes Mellitus is estimated to be around 1.7 trillion dollars [3]. This will affect the government's efforts in attaining Indonesia's Golden Generation in 2045.

Molecular docking study used aleglitazar, a balanced dual peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor α/γ (PPAR α/γ) agonist (PDB ID: 3G9E). Aleglitazar has potential treatment

of hyperglycaemia and dyslipidemia in patients with Type II Diabetes Mellitus [4]. Both PPAR α and γ are expressed in the kidney, and their agonists exhibit renoprotective effects in type 2 diabetes [5]. PPAR γ agonists used to involved in glucose homeostasis, insulin sensitivity in peripheral insulin-sensitive tissues, and lipid storage [5]. In the research, Aleglitazar has a lack of cardiovascular efficacy and peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor-related side effects in patients with type 2 diabetes post-acute coronary syndrome [6]. In high dose Aleglitazar (600 μ g/day), increased incidence of expected PPAR class side effects. The side effects is peripheral edema, weight gain, and congestive heart failure [7].

Many of the commonly used drugs today are structurally derived from natural plants that exist in traditional medicinal plants originating from Indonesia. Some Indonesian plants that have the potential antidiabetic activity are as follows:

Table 1. Native Indonesian plant that have antidiabetic activity

Medicinal Plants	Indonesian Name	Active Ingredients
<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>	Kayu manis	Flavonol A [8]
<i>Syzygium polyanthum</i>	Salam	Polifenol [9]
<i>Dioscorea bulbifera</i>	Tanaman Gembolo	Diosgenin [10]
<i>Aloe vera</i>	Lidah buaya	Antraquinon [11]
<i>Phaleria macrocarpa</i>	Mahkota Dewa	Saponin [12]
<i>Eleutherine bulbosa</i>	Bawang Dayak	Eleutherinoside A [13]
<i>Tinospora crispa</i> (L.)	Brotowali	Andrografolid [14]
<i>Cananga odorata</i>	Kenanga	Terpenoid [15]
<i>Parkia roxburghii</i>	Kedawung	Phytosterol [16]
<i>Centella asiatica</i>	Pegagan	Terpenoid, Coumarin [17]

In this research, we were looking for new substances to alter Aleglitazar made from Indonesia herbal medicine by molecular docking studies. Therefore, there will be a new reference for alternative therapy that has more effectivity with less toxicity for patient with Diabetes Mellitus.

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Selection of Plant

The selection of plants is done by searching Indonesia herbal medicine and the active substance of the plants has been proven to have antidiabetic activity

Molecular Docking Simulation

This study was conducted by “in silico” method. Aleglitazar and 3G9E was derived from www.rcsb.org. Visualization of ligand and receptor interactions was conducted by BIOVIA Discovery Studio 2016. 2D structures of each active compounds was built by ChemBioDraw Ultra 12.0. 2D structures that were transformed to 3D structures by ChemBio3D Ultra 12.0 with AM1 semi empiric minimization method. This minimization method was purposed to produce an accurate geometrical structure.. Molecular docking simulation was conducted by AutoDock Tools 1.5.6.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Validation of Docking Simulation

Docking validation procedure was implemented by redocking Aleglitazar to 3G9E. to ensure that docking application could produce valid result. Docking method was valid if the interaction between receptor and ligand was the same with crystal structure, and RMSD value was $<2 \text{ \AA}$ [18].

Figure 1. Overlay of ligand position of Aleglitazar from redocking result (green) and crystallography result (grey).

Visualization of crystallography and redocking showed the same result that is formed hydrogen bond with TYR473 and SER289.

Table 2. Results of molecular docking simulation validation

Receptor	3G9E
Ligand	Aleglitazar
RMSD (\AA)	1,9
ΔG (kcal/mol)	-11,04
KI (nM)	8,15 nM
Amino acid residues	TYR473, SER289, HIS323, ILE341, LEU330, TYR327, GLY284
Number of hydrogen bond	2

Molecular Docking Simulation

Aleglitazar and each active compounds were docked to 3G9E (Table 3).

Table 3. Results of molecular docking simulation

Natural Compound	Free Energy Binding/ ΔG (kcal/mol)	KI
Androgra-pholide	-8.46	549.3 nM
Antraquinon	-8.08	1.19 uM
Asiaticoside	-7.4	2.81 uM
Cuminy Alcohol	-5.71	61.05 u

Diosgenin	-8.20	971.94 nM
Glycyrrizha	-8.34	774.63 nM
Saponin	-7.21	2.16 uM
Terpenoid	-7.61	2.63 uM
Phytosterol	-9.41	62.12 nM
Eleuterino- shide	-8.13	1.11 uM

According to table 3, Andrographolide, Glycyrrizha and Phytosterol have the smallest Free Energy Binding among other compounds. ΔG value was described strength of bond, if more negative of ΔG value the bond was stronger [19].

Figure 2. Visualization of Andrographolide (Interaction between Andrographolide with binding site)

Figure 2 shows that amino acid residues that form bonds with andrographolide compounds are amino acid residues TYR473, PHE363 and MET364 (hydrogen bond), LEU330, ARG288

Figure 3. Visualization of Phytosterol (Interaction between Phytosterol with binding site)

Figure 3 shows that phytosterols do not show hydrogen bonds. The amino acid residue and the position of the result docking compound from its active site despite having a good Free Energy Binding (not recommended).

Figure 4. Visualization of Glycyrrizha (Interaction between Glycyrrizha with binding site)

Figure 4 shows that Glycyrrizha do not show hydrogen bonds. Same as phytosterols, the amino acid residue and the position of the result docking compound from its active site despite having a good Free Energy Binding (not recommended).

From these three results, it can be concluded that the best compound for PPAR α/γ receptor in improving insulin sensitivity is andrographolide from *Tinospora crispa* plant (Brotowali Plant) because the amino acid residue that is formed is similar to the complex ligand with its agonist receptor. Free energy binding of andrographolide ($\Delta G = -8.46$ kcal / mol) more large than aleglitazar ($\Delta G = -11.04$ kcal / mol) is expected to provide good effectiveness and less toxicity for patient with Diabetes Mellitus.

CONCLUSION

Based on the molecular docking study, Indonesia herbal medicine which has the best activity for PPAR α / γ receptor in improving insulin sensitivity is andrografolid compound ($\Delta G = -8.46$ kcal / mol). Andrografolid is a natural compound contained in the plant Brotowali (*Tinospora crispa*). Therefore, it can be concluded that the brotowali plant is the best herbal medicine Indonesia that can be used for patient with Type II Diabetes Mellitus. Thus the prevalence of Diabetes Mellitus in Indonesia will decrease. This condition is expected to increase GDP (Gross Domestic Product) to attaining Indonesia's Golden Generation in 2045.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

We declare that we have no conflict of interest in the authorship or publication of this contribution.

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